

THE ROLE OF MODERN ARCHITECTURE IN THE DEFINITION OF THE PORTUGUESE HEALTH SYSTEM

STUDY OF TWO PARTICULAR CASES

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Being health a fundamental right, the healthcare system and infrastructures are essential for society's wellbeing and progress¹. Specially in the context we face since 2020 with the Covid-19 Pandemic, this is once again in the fore.

1. HEALTHCARE ARCHITECTURE AND MODERN MOVEMENT IN PORTUGAL. THE DEFINITION OF THE PORTUGUESE HEALTH SYSTEM

As the relationship between illness and the built environment is undoubtedly a critical topic, architecture and medicine have always been tightly interlinked. Investigation into healthcare buildings involves dealing with multiple spheres beyond the technological, physical, and psychological. Nowadays, the growing emphasis on wellbeing goes beyond the seminal ideas of the hospital as a "healing machine", or that architecture and urbanism were shaped by bacteria, influenced by discoveries made by physicians as Louis Pasteur (1822-1895), Robert Koch (1843-1910), and Wilhelm Conrad Röntgen (1845-1923), which were decisive for the recognition of the diseases as pathologies and the hospitals as 'instruments' and places for their healing. Until then, hospitals were mostly not viewed as cure and care spaces, but places where sick people were isolated from the society in order to avoid the spread of pests and epidemic diseases.

As in many other European countries, Portugal assisted to a huge development of its healthcare assistance facilities since mid-19th century, beginning of the 20th century.

Following the extinction of the religious orders in 1834, which left the spaces they had used unoccupied, many of these were reused in new ways, with most of them being turned into hospitals, as it happened namely in Lisbon. In the second half of the 19th century, Portugal assisted to the construction of its first specialised paediatric hospital, the D. Estefânia, designed by Albert Jenkins Humbert (1821-1877). To fight tuberculosis, a network of sanatoria and dispensary was started to be set up with the founding of the *Assistência Nacional aos Tuberculosos* [National Assistance to Tuberculosis Patients, ANT] in 1899². Thus, marked by the combat of tuberculosis, architecture of the early 20th century was highly influenced by the basic combat rules – ventilation, fresh air, and sunlight – which in association with the use of new materials came to acquire a primary importance in the development of

1. As Susan Sontag writes: "Illness is the night-side of life, a more onerous citizenship. Everyone who is born holds dual citizenship, in the kingdom of the well and in the kingdom of the sick. Although we all prefer to use only the good passport, sooner or later each of us is obliged, at least for a spell, to identify ourselves as citizens of that other place", in SONTAG, Susan, *Illness as a Metaphor*, Farrar, Straus and Giroux, New York, 1978, p. 3.
2. Founded as philanthropic association by D. Amélia (1865-1951) on 11th June 1899.

architecture, here assuming often the pavilion typology. Besides sanatoria, in Portugal, the pavilion typology was mainly adopted for specialized healthcare facilities, namely psychiatric, oncologic, or for infectious diseases.

With the Modern Movement, new architecture theories and tendencies came up, highly influenced by the political, economic, cultural, and social changes. Like in other architecture fields, also in healthcare architecture great changes could be noted. Especially relevant are the theories about the humanization of hospitals and their organization regarding the balance between the quality of spaces and functional and economic efficiency, evidencing a strong relation to “the medical body in Modern Architecture”³. Representative architects were Alvar Aalto (1898-1976), Le Corbusier (1886-1965), Ernst Kopp (1890-1962) and Hermann Distel (1875-1945). Further, since the interwar period, new hospital typologies have been adopted: instead of the pavilion typology, the vertical typology was desired, as in this way spaces and circulations are more concentrated and consequently the hospitals’ efficiency is higher. Remarkable examples are the *Hôpital Beaujon* in Clichy, Paris (1933-1935), by Jean Walter (1883-1957), the *Södersjukhuset* in Stockholm (1937-1944) by Hjalmar Cederström (1880-1953), or the Columbia-Presbyterian Medical Center (1925-1932) in New York, by James Gamble Rogers (1867-1947). In Portugal it was first applied by Hermann Distel in both, Santa Maria (1938-1953) and São João (1938-1959) Hospitals, in Lisbon and Porto respectively.

In parallel to the definition of the anti-tuberculosis network by ANT in Portugal, the reform of the health, hygiene, and welfare services was a major concern as the general health conditions were still very poor. Therefore, the *Direcção-Geral de Saúde e Beneficência Pública* [Directorate-General of Public Health and Welfare, DGS] was founded in 1899, having as first major action the definition of the General Regulation of Health Services and Public Welfare, that entered into force in 1903, inaugurating health as a “public matter”. The “Medical Generation of 1911” had here a protagonist role in the implementation of a series of initiatives that transformed care and scientific research in the field of medicine in Portugal. Several important healthcare buildings were built in this period, as their construction, promoted by the medical teaching class, motivated by scientific research, the development of medical teaching, and the mission of caring for the population, had with the support of the state and other benefactor⁴. But, due to the political instability at the time and in the coming years, it was only in 1933 after the establishment of the *Estado Novo* and under António de Oliveira Salazar’s (1889-1970) dictatorship, that the definition of a structured network to fight tuberculosis based on different building typologies, and the construction of new teaching hospitals in Lisbon and Porto, found the legal mechanisms for their development.

However, despite the plans and efforts made to improve the country’s health conditions, and the response of its healthcare facilities, until the Trigo de Negreiros Health Reform⁵ in 1945, medical assistance in Portugal had neither a structured network nor a global strategic thinking, and there was no specialized body for the coordination and design of healthcare buildings. It was just with it that the strategic support mechanisms to the creation of the *Comissão de Construções Hospitalares* [Hospital Construction Commission, CCH]⁶, founded in 1946 by Law no. 2011, were established, investing in the reorganisation of the network of central and local services.

3. COLOMINA, Beatriz, *X-Ray Architecture*, Lars Müller Publishers, Baden, 2019.

4. Among them the Alfredo da Costa Maternity (1908-1932), the Júlio de Matos Hospital (1912-1942) and the Portuguese Institute of Oncology (1927-1975), in Lisbon; the Sant’Ana Sanatorium in Parede (1901-1904); the Sousa Martins Sanatorium in Guarda (1907); or the Caramulo Sanatorial Resort (1920-1954). See TOSTÕES, Ana, ARNAUT, Daniela, PROVIDÊNCIA, Paulo (ed.), *Curar e Cuidar. Arquitetura da Saúde em Portugal (1901-1976)*, IST-ID, Lisboa, 2020.

5. Law-Decree n. 35 108, 7th November 1945, named after Joaquim Trigo de Negreiros (1900-1976).

6. The CCH was renamed in 1971 to Direcção Geral das Construções Hospitalares [General Directorate of Hospital Construction, DGCH], which in turn passed to Direcção Geral das Instalações e Equipamentos de Saúde [General Directorate of Health Facilities and Equipment, DGIES] in 1985.

Thus, the desired universal access to health care became enshrined through the terms of the Portuguese Constitution in 1976, consolidated in 1979, with the creation of the *Serviço Nacional de Saúde* [National Health Service, SNS], in accordance with the Order of 29 July 1978 by António Arnaut (1936-2018)⁷.

2. TWO MODERN HOSPITALS: FROM THE PROJECT TO NOWADAYS

2.1. Hospital de São João, Porto

Hospital de São João (1938-1959) in Porto is the “twin” of *Hospital de Santa Maria* (1938-1953) in Lisbon⁸, both designed by Hermann Distel (1875-1945) and being the main teaching hospitals in Portugal.

Their history dates back to 1825, when the Royal Schools of Surgery were founded, incorporated in the *Hospital Real de S. José* and the *Hospital Real de Santo António*, in Lisbon and Porto, respectively. In 1836, the Royal Schools of Surgery were elevated to Medical-Surgical Schools. Since the beginning of the 20th century, the “Medical Generation of 1911” aimed to reform the medical education in Portugal, seeking to modernize it and bring it closer to European teaching models, being less theoretical and more practical, as well as the construction of two proper teaching hospitals, one in Lisbon and the other one in Porto.

However, even having been created in 1919 a commission chaired by Francisco Gentil (1878-1964) to establish a structure and programme for the construction of the two new teaching hospitals, only in 1933 was ordered “the construction of two teaching hospitals, one in Lisbon and the other in Porto, linked to their respective Faculties of Medicine”, which were to be “designed in accordance with the same technical principles as hospitals, and have a capacity of 1500 beds each”, with the difference that the hospital in Porto should “be planned to be built in two phases, with 600 to 800 beds to be fully available after completion of the first phase of the works” by Decree-Law no. 22 917⁹. Therefore, in 1934, Eng. Duarte Pacheco (1899-1943), instituted the *Comissão Administrativa dos Novos Edifícios Universitários* [Administrative Commission for New University Buildings, CANEU]¹⁰ through Decree no. 24776, which had to direct and administrate the construction of new hospitals through a specialized Technical Commission – the *Comissão Técnica dos Hospitais Escolares* [Technical Commission for Teaching Hospitals]¹¹.

After conducting a survey of all the professors of the Faculties of Medicine of Lisbon and Porto, studying the program for the new hospitals, analysing the implemented model in new American university hospitals¹², visiting modern hospitals in other European countries¹³, and attending to the 4th International Hospital Congress of the International Hospital Association (IHA), in 1935 in Rome, Francisco Gentil invited in January 1938 the German architect Hermann Distel – internationally recognized as one of the best hospital architects at that time and then president of the Building Sector of the IHA –, to conceive the project for both teaching hospitals. Francisco Gentil considered him “the most perfect and cognizant architect on the hospital question”¹⁴.

7. Thus known as 'Despacho Arnaut'.

8. COUTINHO, Joana, *A Arquitetura da cura e os equipamentos hospitalares. Dois hospitais modernos em Portugal*, Integrated Master's Thesis, Instituto Superior Técnico, Lisboa, 2019; ARNAUT, Daniela, *Edifícios de Saúde em Portugal (1927-1958). O espaço de cura: entre forma e função*, PhD Thesis, Instituto Superior Técnico, Lisboa, 2020; ARNAUT, Daniela, COUTINHO, Joana, “Hospitais Escolares de Lisboa e do Porto”, in Ana Tostões, Daniela Arnaut, Paulo Providência, *Curar e Cuidar. Arquitetura da Saúde em Portugal (1901-1979)*, IST-ID, Lisboa, 2020, pp. 218-223; ARNAUT, Daniela, “Hospital de Santa Maria”, in Ana Tostões, Daniela Arnaut, Paulo Providência, *Curar e Cuidar. Arquitetura da Saúde em Portugal (1901-1979)*, IST-ID, Lisboa, 2020, pp. 224-235; COUTINHO, Joana, “Hospital de São João”, in Ana Tostões, Daniela Arnaut, Paulo Providência, *Curar e Cuidar. Arquitetura da Saúde em Portugal (1901-1979)*, IST-ID, Lisboa, 2020, pp. 236-247.

9. Law-Decree n. 22917, 31st July 1933, p. 1498.

10. The CANEU consisted of Prof. Alexandre Alberto Sousa Pinto (1880-1982), Senior Public Works Inspector Engineer Fernando Jácome de Castro (1892-1964), Prof. Engineer Manuel Tavares Cardoso (1892-1969), Engineer Eduardo Evangelista do Carvalho (1885-1972) and Dr. Domingos António Alvarez. In 1957, this commission became the *Comissão Administrativa das Novas Instalações Universitárias* [Administrative Commission for New University Facilities, CANIU].

11. The Technical Commission for Teaching Hospital was composed by Prof. Dr. Francisco Gentil, Prof. Dr. Hernâni Monteiro, Engineer Fernando Jácome de Castro, Prof. Engineer Manuel Tavares Cardoso, Engineer Eduardo Evangelista do Carvalho, and Administrator Mário Neves (1914-1999).

12. Namely the School of Medicine and Hospital of Vanderbilt University (1923) in Tennessee, the Columbia-Presbyterian Medical Center (1925-1932) in New York, designed by James Gamble Rogers (1867-1947), or the Cornell Medical Center (1929-1932) designed by Coolidge, Shepley, Bulfinch and Abbott. See: ARNAUT, Daniela, COUTINHO, Joana, op. cit., p. 219.

13. In particular the San Carlos University Hospital (1928-1936), in Madrid, designed by Manuel Sánchez Arcas (1897-1970), the Grande Hospital de Viterbo (1933), of Ettore Rossi (1894-1968), and the Hôpital de Beaujon (1932-1935) in Clichy, Paris designed by Jean Walter (1883-1957). Idem., p. 219.

14. GENTIL, Francisco, “Apontamentos sobre o problema dos hospitais escolares”, in *Jornal do Médico*, June 1952, n. 69-72, p. 4.

Fig. 1. Hermann Distel, *Hospital de São João*, Porto, Portugal, 1938-1959. Diagram "relationship between the areas of the hospital and of the faculty". © GENTIL, Francisco, ATHIAS, Marck (ed.), *Separata do Arquivo de Patologia*, additional number of vol. XI, December 1939.

Between January 1938 and June 1939, Hermann Distel worked out 12 preliminary drafts, being the last version approved by Salazar and Duarte Pacheco in February 1939: with capacity for 1500 beds and 675 students, the chosen version “concentrates in just one building (...) the teaching, investigation and healthcare and social assistance facilities, creating a real medical centre for cultural and professional guidance”¹⁵. The resulting building was a model project whose layout was oriented to provide adequate solar exposure, being the several medical services arranged around a vertical circulation system, with the distances between inpatient services and diagnosis- and treatment spaces rigorously calculated to ensure optimal economic and functional efficiency and comfort, in accordance with his previously-published theoretical studies¹⁶. According to Distel, the monobloc typology, due to its spatial concentration¹⁷,

“allows minimum construction costs, minimum maintenance costs [and] better functioning to be achieved: by virtue of reducing the distances to be covered, saving the doctors time and the staff energy; and furthermore – most importantly – providing better conditions for patients.”

To illustrate this, the final drawings were accompanied by a series of diagrams¹⁸ (Fig. 1), stating hereby the rigour, detail, and rationality of his work in the hospital design. Furthermore, in seeking to reach an ideal design of a hospital space, and thus, following the design of a model project deeply influenced by the rationalism and the representation of power, the similarities of the project for the teaching hospitals of Lisbon and Porto with the at the time ongoing project for the Berlin University Hospital (not built) are evident¹⁹.

As teaching hospitals, the new hospitals should be built near the new University Campus of Lisbon and Porto, also in construction at that time. As they were thought as twins, Distel created the preliminary draft and project just for Lisbon, the project being afterwards adapted for Porto. Consequently, it “did not consider the soil conditions of the plot where the hospital would be built neither the future urban framing of that area”²⁰. However, due to World War II the construction of both hospitals only started in 1944 (Lisbon) and 1945 (Porto), reflecting once again, the primacy of the Lisbon hospital.

15. GENTIL, Francisco, ATHIAS, Marck (ed.), *Separata do Arquivo de Patologia*, December 1939, additional number of vol. XI, p. 2.

16. Namely DISTEL, Hermann, *Krankenhäuser*, Hegner, Hellerau, 1931; DISTEL, Hermann, *Rationeller Krankenhaus-Bau*, Kohlhammer Verlag, Stuttgart, 1932.

17. DISTEL, Hermann, “Memória descritiva”, in Francisco Gentil, Marck Athias, *Separata do Arquivo de Patologia*, December 1939, additional number of vol. XI, p. 30.

18. Related to: the orientation of the building, the areas of the hospital and the faculty; the distribution of the inpatient clinics; access and circulation – level -2 “contaminated”, level -1 “clean” and students’ entrance, level 1 patients’ entrance, level 2 visitors’ entrance; and the relationship between the polyclinics, the diagnostic and treatment areas, and the inpatient areas.

19. PAWLIK, Peter R., *Von Bergedorf nach Germania: Hermann Distel (1875-1945) – Ein Architektenleben in bewegter Zeit*, Verlag Murken-Altrogge, Herzogenrath, 2009.

20. GOMES, Ricardo Miguel, *Hospital de São João: 50 anos de sonho e resistência*, Hospital de São João, Porto, 2009, p. 37.

Fig. 2. Hermann Distel, *Hospital de São João*, Porto, Portugal, 1938-1959. Aerial view, 1963. © Arquivo Histórico da Câmara Municipal do Porto.

Planned to have a total of 11 floors, 2 of them underground, the hospitals are composed of two big longitudinal parallel blocks – the south one with “saw-tooth” design –, linked through three transversal blocks, and punctuated by outward-projecting “turrets”. Hereby, three courtyards were formed: to the east, the services courtyard; in the centre, the interior courtyard with the technical centre; and to the west, the interior courtyard for the students.

Although having been designed by Distel as “twin” hospitals, their construction made them different as, unlike to Lisbon, the construction of the teaching hospital in Porto was since the very beginning planned to be built in two phases, as stated above. So, in the first phase the four “turrets” up from level 2 were left unconstructed (Fig. 2). Consequently, some medical services had to be combined, since all services were an essential pre-condition for the status of renowned teaching hospital. However, the site conditions, which were not considered in Distel’s model project, turned out necessary to extend the foundations down to the lowest quota, allowing, thus, an initial capacity of already almost 1,200 beds, without an effective reduction of the total construction area.

As teaching hospital, and identically to Lisbon, the building concentrates all the spaces corresponding to the triplet of assistance, teaching and investigation: the medical services are organized vertically, mainly in the south longitudinal block and in the four “turrets”; the emergency services, the outpatient consultations (polyclinics) and day hospital, and the central surgical suite, are placed along the north longitudinal block; the laboratories, the diagnosis and treatment services, as well as the administrative and management services, the cafeterias, the staff facilities, the technical, industrial and supply services, and a chapel are housed in the transversal wings; and the medical faculty and research spaces, namely the classrooms assigned by institute, with amphitheatres for theoretical teaching, small amphitheatres for practical teaching, and a large amphitheatre, as well as a library, are located both in the north longitudinal block and in the transversal blocks, with the main entrance to the faculty located on level -1 and, thus, direct access to the students’ courtyard.

Fig. 3. Hermann Distel, *Hospital de São João*, Porto, Portugal, 1938-1959. Plan of level 5: central surgical suite (to the north) and inpatient areas (to the south). © Ministério das Obras Públicas, Comissão Administrativa das Novas Instalações Universitárias, *Hospital de S. João e Faculdade de Medicina*, Ministério das Obras Públicas, Porto, 1959. Arquivo Histórico da Secretaria Geral da Educação e Ciência.

Special attention was given to the layout of the inpatient clinical units (Fig. 3). These were organized vertically into medical units with, in rule, 27 beds, being the wards always located on the exterior façade facing south, thus benefiting from good sunlight and natural ventilation: the layout of the beds parallel to the façade was such that it provides greater comfort to the patients, avoiding glare from sunlight; the 3.10 m ceiling height ensured compliance with hygiene and air circulation standards, and a human scale that made patients feel more comfortable.

The architect's concern for the health of those who worked in the hospital, namely the importance of natural light, was also evident in the central surgical suite, as its location in the north building (Fig. 3) allowed the entrance of natural light through frosted glass windows without causing glare, and included a shading system for high precision surgery. Furthermore, its location next to the faculty, and the possibility of observing from an upper-level gallery, in 4 of the operating theatres, strengthened the connection with teaching²¹.

Thus, a close link was established between the hospital and the faculty, while the polyclinic became a "centre for the screening and distribution of patients"²², from where they were referred for observation, diagnosis, or treatment services, or distributed to the inpatient units. Accesses and circulations of patients, medical personnel, students, visitors, staff, and goods, materials and equipment were independent and occurred at different levels, avoiding interferences with each other (Fig. 4).

Its design follows, thus, a clear monobloc layout²³:

"that imposed itself through the dominating and austere design of its volumes, clad in a monumental uniform skin that responded effectively to the scale of the building. (...) Where the standardized design of the openings was overridden, it was to reinforce the axial symmetry that gave the building its monumentality."

21. COUTINHO, Joana, 2019, op. cit., p. 40.

22. DISTEL, Hermann op. cit., p. 31.

23. ARNAUT, Daniela, op. cit.

Fig. 4. Hermann Distel, *Hospital de São João*, Porto, Portugal, 1938-1959. View of the main entrance body: students' entrance (below, level -1), and visitors' entrance trough access ramps (above, level 2). © Joana Coutinho, 2019.

Baptised as *Hospital de São João*, the Porto teaching hospital was inaugurated on 24th June 1959, after the completion of the first construction phase, but unfortunately already after the death of Hermann Distel, the work being continued by his son Walter Distel. It was considered as one of the best examples for hospital architecture of the Modern Movement, or, as Jácome de Castro stated, “an exceptional work in every respect.”²⁴

However, as the second construction phase was never executed, soon problems were realised in the hospital: namely the need of own bigger spaces in terms of both consultation and inpatient areas for several services²⁵. Consequently, several interventions were made to enlarge and remodel some areas, in an effort to respond to the needs of space, services, care, research and teaching. Unfortunately, until the beginning of the 21st century, in the absence of long-term planning, “interventions were carried out only addressing immediate requirements, and furthermore, the hospital’s architecture was rarely properly considered, resulting in interventions that disfigured its interior and exterior.”²⁶ As a countermeasure, since 2007, in conjunction with ARIPA Arquitectos, a strategic plan for the remodelling, modernization and expansion of the hospital has been developed, taking a global and long-term view, which considers the architectural value of the hospital and its important role in the Portuguese health system, as a recognized hospital, with a 1,105-bed capacity and 33 medical and surgical specialities.

2.2. Hospital de Santa Luzia, Viana do Castelo

Designed by the Portuguese architect Raúl Chorão Ramalho (1914-2002), the *Hospital Distrital de Santa Luzia* in Viana do Castelo (1970-1984)²⁷, is one of the most relevant examples of the brutalist architecture in Portugal and one of his major public work of reference.²⁸

The hospital of Viana do Castelo is one of the 15 regional hospitals that the CCH ordered to be built within the III. Development Plan (1968-1973) to develop and improve the health care network in Portugal, which at the time was still

24. Ministério das Obras Públicas, Comissão Administrativa das Novas Instalações Universitárias, *Faculdade de Medicina e Hospital de São João*, Ministério das Obras Públicas, Porto, 1959, p. 3. Arquivo Histórico do Ministério das Obras Públicas.

25. The first interventions date from 1964, involving the expansion of the emergency service. For further details see COUTINHO, Joana, 2019, op. cit.

26. COUTINHO, Joana, 2020, op. cit., p. 238.

27. COUTINHO, Joana, 2019, op. cit.; TOSTÕES, Ana, COUTINHO, Joana, “Hospital de Santa Luzia” in Ana Tostões, Daniela Arnaut, Paulo Providência, *Curar e Cuidar. Arquitetura da Saúde em Portugal (1901-1979)*, IST-ID, Lisboa, 2020, pp. 298-309.

28. TOSTÕES, Ana, “A monumentalidade como programa político e simbólico do Estado Novo”, in Joana Brites, Luís Miguel Correia, *Obras Públicas do Estado Novo*, Imprensa da Universidade de Coimbra, Coimbra, 2019; TOSTÕES, Ana, *Os Verdes Anos na Arquitetura Portuguesa*, FAUP Publicações, Porto, 1997.

Fig. 5. Map of the division of the country, 1948. Leaflet: Comissão Administrativa dos Novos Edifícios Universitários, *15 Anos de Obras Públicas (1932-1947) – Organização Hospitalar* [hospital organization], 1948. Arquivo Histórico do Ministério das Obras Públicas.

relatively poor. Therefore, based on the healthcare system organization of Law no. 2011, “the country was to be divided into zones, regions and sub-regions” and “in each zone there will be at least one central hospital; in each region one regional hospital; in each sub-region one sub-regional hospital”²⁹ (Fig. 5). After studying the map of healthcare facilities in Portugal, in the 1940s, it was realised that most of these were concentrated in large urban centres, with a clear deficiency in the interior and north of the country. In this context, the Viana do Castelo region was identified as one of the areas where there was a shortage of medical care³⁰, so the CCH considered it essential to build a regional hospital in the city of Viana do Castelo, the district capital, to ensure the healthcare assistance of the region of Viana do Castelo. Thus, in January 1970, Raúl Chorão Ramalho, who already had designed the Beja Regional Hospital within the same Development Plan, was appointed to design the Viana do Castelo Hospital, in collaboration with the architect Leonel Clérigo.

Located at the foothills of *Monte de Santa Luzia*, the hospital lies on the transition from the urban area to the green spot of the Santa Luzia Temple-Monument³¹, on a plot with a steep slope and facing the Lima river. Thus, the site’s location and topography were decisive for the architectural design of the building, specifically in terms of its volume, as, according to Chorão Ramalho “it was necessary to create a solution that corresponded to a correct functional scheme for the hospital, while conciliating it with a volumetry that could mitigate the unavoidable impact of the building on the city’s panorama”³². This being said, a compact vertical solution was unfeasible. In consequence, still during the preparation of early studies for the building’s footprint, he realised that the area of the site was insufficient. So, in 1972, as there were adjacent plots available, the area of the site for the construction of the hospital was increased such that it allowed the design of a solution with an adequate volume and respective access areas.

29. Law n. 2011, 2nd April 1946, p. 201.

30. “With a population of around 70,000 inhabitants in 1950, hospital care in Viana do Castelo, was provided in three different buildings: medical care in the Hospital da Misericórdia, in the city’s historical centre, surgery in the surgical pavilion located at Monte de Santa Luzia, and maternity and paediatrics in the pavilion of the old Nursing Home at the foot of Monte de Santa Luzia. These buildings had poor quality facilities and a total capacity of 150 beds”, in COUTINHO, Joana, 2019, op. cit., p. 55.

31. The site chosen for the construction of the new hospital comprised the site of the pavilion of the old Nursing Home, which was to be maintained, and the adjacent available land.

32. RAMALHO, Raúl Chorão, “Hospital Distrital Viana do Castelo”, undated, p. 4. Arquivo da Administração Central do Sistema de Saúde.

Fig. 6. Raúl Chorão Ramalho, *Hospital de Santa Luzia*, Viana do Castelo, Portugal, 1970-1984. View of the hospital and the foot of *Monte de Santa Luzia* from the Lima river. © "Trabalhos do Arquitecto Chorão Ramalho: Hospital Distrital de Viana do Castelo", *Arquitectura*, 4th series, n. 151, January-April 1983.

Having been the project approved in January 1974, the construction of the hospital started in 1976. However, still in the same year, the architect was asked to deliver an expert report on the feasibility of increasing the hospital's capacity from around 300 beds to nearly 500 beds, and the inclusion of new inpatient services, an additional operating theatre in the central surgical suite, as well as a mental health service with external consultation and inpatient areas. Therefore, 6 hypotheses for the hospital expansion were studied by the architect, who then explained the recommended hypothesis, based on the same criteria and concerns as in the initial project. After both the report and the recommended solution having been approved in 1977 by the DGCH, Chorão Ramalho designed the expansion project for the hospital until 1978, guided mainly by the concern of minimizing changes in the organisational scheme proposed in the initial project and avoiding significant interference with works in progress. This involved the construction of the new inpatient block to the north of the building already under construction, with a link to the old Pavilion of the Nursing Home reusing it, and thus, attending the DGCH's desire of not demolish it, and connecting this new block to the in construction building by extending the main north-south circulation axis, so that its orientation was similar to that of the other inpatient blocks, but with a slight inflection towards the west to make it parallel to the Nursing Home pavilion and give it a wider view over the surroundings and the mouth of the Lima river. It extended to the west, set back from the rest, such that the overall image of the complex was not disrupted when seen from the river or the city (Fig. 6). So, its incorporation "into the hospital complex, allowed the clinical units and related services to be concentrated

7

Fig. 7. Raúl Chorão Ramalho, *Hospital de Santa Luzia*, Viana do Castelo, Portugal, 1970-1984. View over the interior courtyards. © CuCa_RE, 2018.

Fig. 8. Raúl Chorão Ramalho, *Hospital de Santa Luzia*, Viana do Castelo, Portugal, 1970-1984. Axonometric perspective of the hospital with location of the services and entrances. © "Trabalhos do Arquitecto Chorão Ramalho: Hospital Distrital de Viana do Castelo", *Arquitectura*, 4th series, n. 151, January-April 1983.

8

on the same floors without the need for long journeys, either to the central surgical suite, or to the main vertical access hub³³, and the construction of a psychiatric inpatient unit.

Consequently, the hospital was built in 3 phases: the first phase, between February 1976 and February 1981, comprised the construction of the initial building, including the modifications resulting from the increase of the hospital's capacity; the second phase, between April 1981 and December 1982, corresponded the adjustments and extension of the initial building towards north, with all the services essential for the proper functioning of the hospital; and in the third phase, between January 1983 and January 1984, was built the north block containing the new inpatient units, concluding the construction of the hospital. Its inauguration followed shortly after, on 6th January 1984, with the hospital having a total capacity of 488 beds.

Seeking to respond, on one hand to the functional programme, the health-care requirements, the need of being built in a short time, and the site characteristics, and, on the other hand, to the desire of creating interior spaces of high quality, in terms of natural lighting, ventilation and visual contact with the surroundings, the resulting volumetric design of the hospital consisted of a total of 8 floors, 2 of which partially embedded in the hill due to the slope of the site. Based on a raster of 3.85 x 3.85 m, corresponding to an inpatient ward module, the structure and organisation of the hospital floors consist in the reproduction of this module, so that the raster functions as structuring element of the whole hospital, and resulted in a building composed of parallelepiped volumes, and juxtaposed perpendicularly or parallelly, according to their programme requirements (Fig. 7).

The lower levels (-1, 0 and 1) were functionally arranged around courtyards (Fig. 8), while the upper levels (2 to 6), dedicated to the inpatient clinical units, were developed linearly and parallel to the river. The main entrance was located on level 0, with its big hall functioning as structural element for the

33. RAMALHO, Raúl Chorão, "Parecer sobre a viabilidade de aumento de lotação do Hospital Distrital de Viana do Castelo", 1976, p. 8. Direção Geral do Património Cultural / Sistema de Informação para o Património Arquitectónico, Arquivo do Forte de Sacavém, Espólio RCR (199) RCR-TXT-71.

Fig. 9: Raúl Chorão Ramalho, *Hospital de Santa Luzia*, Viana do Castelo, Portugal, 1970-1984. Plan of level 2: central surgical suite and inpatient areas. Original design, redraw. © Joana Coutinho, 2019.

circulations, as distribution point of patients, medical staff, and visitors to the proper circulations. At this level were located all services with a significant flow of users: the emergency service, outpatient consultations, diagnosis and treatment services, administrative and management services, and the hospital's direction. Directly above, a technical floor was created, that functions as transition level to the inpatient levels. Occupying levels 2 to 6, the inpatient services were organised into 34-bed inpatient units, with the wards facing south towards the river, providing this way the spaces with good natural lighting and ventilation and a visual connection to the outside surroundings (Fig. 9). The central surgical suite was also located on level 2. At the lowest level (-1), were situated the maternal-infant outpatient consultations, the psychiatry, the day hospital, and the chapel.

This way, the architecture of the hospital reflects the deep study of the functional programme made by Chorão Ramalho, namely the pursuit of a solution that fulfilled the functional requirements, provided a good quality of life, and was of fast construction as it had to be built in a short-time frame. Further, as an opposition to the highly functional appearance of a hospital, Chorão Ramalho included several works of art in its inside, as he did in many other public works. Attention was given as well to the outdoor public space of the hospital site, guaranteed its good integration into the urban fabric of the city and the surrounding landscape.

Although having undergone some interventions, since its opening in 1984, the hospital's organisational structure has not undergone many changes. Many of these interventions were consequence of changes in terms of the requirements of medical services as reflect of the constant medical advances in techniques and technology. On the one hand, there has been a marked

growth in outpatient surgery services and outpatient consultations, and of critical medicine and intermediate and palliative care, and on the other hand, a reduction of the needed inpatient capacity – in this case from 488 to 361 beds. Aware of this, the administration of *Hospital de Santa Luzia* has planned the successive renovation of all the hospital's services, undertaken over the past few years, carrying out their conversion as they become necessary. Hereby, the monitoring of these changes is essential to avoid the collapse of a hospital because it has become obsolete.

3. AND NOWADAYS?

With the progress of medicine and technologies, especially since the 20th century, a continuous specialization and individualization of the different hospital spaces is taking place as they are adapted to a given medical treatment or activity. However it is essential that a structural layout exists so that it allows spaces to be flexible and, thus, adapted to serve different medical services according to what needed, but still assuring the strict cleanness and hygiene requirements of a hospital. This became even more important with the Covid-19 Pandemic, as hospitals were faced daily, in the critical phases, with the challenge of providing medical intensive care assistance to the rising number of Covid-19 patients, while still maintaining the strict separation between Covid and non-Covid areas to avoid the spread of the virus and existence of outbreaks in the non-Covid areas.

Moreover, the advantages of flexible spaces in hospitals were seen to be valuable as they admitted the quick transformation of non-Covid areas in Covid care areas, and this way expanded the hospitals' capacity to assure the universal right to health and access to hospital care.